

Protocol for Socioeconomic inequality and multimorbidity progression in the UK Biobank

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Study information

Description

Multimorbidity, defined as the co-occurrence of two or more long-term conditions (LTCs) in the same in-

dividual and also known as multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs), has become a significant challenge in aging populations (Marengoni et al., 2011). The global prevalence of multimorbidity has increased, affecting approximately 37% of adults (Chowdhury

et al., 2023). Individuals with multimorbidity often experience higher rates of hospitalization, increased treatment burden, reduced physical function, and lower quality of life, as well as higher mortality rates (Skou et al., 2022).

Previous studies have indicated a clear socioeconomic gradient in the prevalence and incidence of multimorbidity, with individuals from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds experiencing distinct patterns of multimorbidity and bearing disproportionate burdens over longer durations (Barnett et al., 2012). However, evidence on the heterogeneity in multimorbidity progression rates remains limited, primarily due to constraints of small sample sizes, short follow-up periods or incomplete medical records. Moreover, the roles of socioeconomic status (SES) and other risk factors in the initiation and progression of multimorbidity are not well understood.

In this study, we aimed to comprehensively examine socioeconomic inequalities in the progression of MLTCs using data from the UK Biobank (UKB). By integrating various sources of medical records, we analyzed patterns of MLTC development over time, with multimorbidity defined based on a set of 80 LTC.

This research will use the UK Biobank Resource under Application Number 81520.

Objectives and hypotheses

We hypothesize there are distinct disease trajectories, and a lower SES is associated with a faster rate of developing multimorbidity. The objectives of the study are: 1. To describe the prevalence and patterns of MLTC in the UKB; 2. To identify and assess distinct MLTC trajectories throughout the follow-up period; 3. To examine how the numbers of LTCs influence the transition rate to the subsequent disease states, and how SES shapes the trajectories over time using multistate models. 4. To estimate the probability of developing additional LTC under different scenarios using simulation models based on the multistate transition analyses.

Design plan

Study type

Observational Study. Data is collected from study subjects that are not randomly assigned to a treatment. This includes surveys, natural experiments, and regression discontinuity designs.

Blinding

No blinding is involved in this study.

Study design

UK Biobank is a population-based health research resource consisting of approximately 500,000 people, aged between 38 years and 73 years, who were recruited between 2004 and 2010 from across the UK. Participants provided a range of information on socio-demographic characteristics, and lifestyle factors via questionnaires and interviews; Anthropometric measures, blood pressure readings, and samples of blood were also taken (data available at www.ukbiobank.ac.uk). A full description of the study design, participants, and quality control (QC) methods have been described in detail previously. Note that we used the baseline survey data to define the socioeconomic and lifestyle status of each participant.

Sampling plan

Existing data

The primary care records were only available for approximately half of the population at the time of analysis linkage. In the current study, we excluded participants who missed demographic information (age, sex), and those who did not have primary care data, leaving 29,936 in the final analysis.

Variables

Measures variables

Exposures

The exposure of interest is SES. 6 indicators of SES are used in the study, including education qualification, education years, family income, employment, Townsend deprivation Index, and Index of multiple deprivation (IMD). All the SES variables were collected from questionnaire at baseline.

Outcomes

The main outcome is MLTC, and the secondary outcome is mortality. In the current study, we included a comprehensive set of 80 LTCs, which were long-term physical or mental health conditions of relevance to middle-aged adults. The 80 specific LTCs were selected based on Delphi recommendation, Barnett study, and other established comorbidity indices (Prior). The presence of LTCs was ascertained by several data sources:

- Hospital admission records (ICD-10 diagnosis code and OPCS-4 for procedures)
- Primary care (Read2 and CTV3)
- Cancer registry
- Self-reported diagnosis in UKB baseline assessment data

The code-lists are available in our Github repository.

MLTC was defined as the number of LTCs from the predefined list of 80 conditions. For each participant, we identified the first diagnosis date of each condition by examining all available data sources. Using these diagnosis dates, we constructed a chronological sequence of disease accumulation for each individual.

All-cause mortality and death date were obtained through death certificates held by the National Health Service (NHS) Information Centre (England).

Covariates

Covariates included date of birth, age at baseline, sex (male/female), and ethnicity (white/nonwhite). Five modifiable lifestyle factors were included in this study, including smoking, alcohol consumption, physical activity, diet, and sleeping.

Analysis plan

Sample

The analytic sample consisted of UK Biobank participants who met two criteria: (1) registration with a UK General Practitioner (GP), and (2) availability of clinical diagnostic data. This sample represented approximately 30% of the total UK Biobank cohort. Participants were censored at death, loss to follow-up, or the end of the study period (October 30, 2022), whichever came first.

Statistical models

Part 1. Description of MLTC in UKB

First, we calculated the overall prevalence of MLTCs within the sample. Second, we analyzed the distribution and prevalence stratified by sex, age groups (35-39, 40-44, 45-49, 50-54, 55-59, 60-64, 65-79, ≥ 80 years), and SES levels. Finally, we identified and ranked the 15 most prevalent chronic conditions.

Part 2. Build the MLTC trajectories throughout the follow-up period

To capture underlying disease progression patterns, we employ latent class growth models. These models estimated two key parameters: latent intercepts (representing baseline number of MLTCs) and

slopes (representing rates of disease accumulation) from the longitudinal data. Random effects were incorporated to account for variability in age and calendar time, allowing for individual differences both within and between trajectory clusters. After identifying distinct trajectory clusters, we characterized each latent class by examining their demographic and socioeconomic profiles, including age, sex, SES, etc.

Part 3. Estimate how SES influences the transition rate of morbidity and mortality.

We will apply multistate models to estimate the transition rates between different LTC states. The analysis will use a Lexis dataset constructed with three time scales: calendar time, age at cohort entry, and time since inclusion. Death will be treated as an absorbing state, which can be reached from any other disease state. Individual follow-up periods will be segmented according to the dates of each LTC diagnosis.

Poisson models will then be employed to estimate how SES and the number of conditions influence subsequent morbidity and mortality rates. We will estimate transition rates between successive MLTC states, ranging from no conditions (0 LTC) through to multiple conditions (10+ LTCs).

- Model 1: Adjusted for age, sex and ethnicity.
- Model 2: Adds SES indicators.
- Model 3: Further adjusts for lifestyle factors.

To visualize disease progression patterns, we will generate box plots showing the sequence of MLTC transitions, and cumulative incidence function curves displaying LTC accumulation over time across different SES groups.

Part 4. Model-Based Projections of MLTC Progression

Using simulations from our multistate model, we will estimate the probability of progressing to each MLTC state at various time points post-study entry, stratified by SES groups. These simulations will project morbidity accumulation probabilities over a 15-year period.

Baseline characteristics of the study population, including sociodemographic factors and risk factors, will be summarized using appropriate descriptive statistics: means and standard deviations for normally distributed continuous variables, medians and interquartile ranges (IQR) for non-normally distributed continuous variables, and counts and percentages for categorical variables.

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.4.1 (2024-06-14). The latent class growth models will be conducted using the ‘lcm’ or ‘flexmix’ package. The multi-state models were constructed using the “Epi” and “popEpi” package.

Transformations

Inference criteria

Data exclusion

Missing data

Exploratory analyses (optional)

Multistate models are complex. A series of models will be tested:

1. Different ways to split the dataset after lexis (by age and period);
2. Linear age and period effect;
3. Non-linear age and period effect;
4. Interactions between SES and other factor, including sex, ethnicity, BMI
5. Left-truncation

References

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